

Parasites of white rice leafhopper *Cofana spectra* (Dist.) [Hemiptera: Cicadellidae] in the Philippines

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Numbers and kinds of parasites attacking the egg, nymphal, and adult stages of *Cofana spectra* (Distant) were recorded during the 1982 wet season at IRRI. Potted rice plants infested with white rice leafhopper eggs laid by a greenhouse colony were set in a rice field each week 29–98 days after transplanting. Four species of egg parasites were recovered, the most prevalent of which was a mymarid — *Gonatocerus cingulatus* Perkins — that parasitized up to 17% of eggs (see figure). *Anagrus flaveolus* Waterhouse, *A. optabilis* (Perkins) (Mymaridae), and *Paracentrobia* sp. (Trichogrammatidae) parasitized less than 6% of eggs. White rice leafhopper nymphs and adults were parasitized by a strepsipteron—*Halictophagus spectrus* Yang — and an unidentified mite of the family Erythracidae. The parasites were recovered from nymphs and adults collected from fields by sweep net and from live adults collected in a walk-in light trap. The strepsipteron parasitized 40–60% of nymphs and adults collected in the field, but parasitized less than 15% of adults collected from the light trap, perhaps indicating that parasitized hoppers are those less capable of flying. The mite occurred less consistently on hopper nymphs and adults but parasitized up to 23% of adults collected in the light trap. The most prevalent parasites of white rice leafhopper — *G. cingulatus*, *H. spectrus*, and the unidentified mite — do not attack the other commonly occurring rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. The egg parasites *A. flaveolus* and *A. optabilis* are most common on the brown planthopper. *Paracentrobia* sp. has a wide host range.

Figure Abundance of white rice leafhopper *Cofana spectra* (Dist.) in rice field, light trap collections, and parasitization of eggs, nymphs, or adults. IRRI, 1982 wet season.

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Egg parasitization (%) Eggs exposed in field (no./date)

Nymph and adult parasitization (%)

White rice leafhopper population

